

1 **Activation of ZNF213-AS1 by HPV16 E7.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We
7 studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-
8 C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of Znf213-as1 by
9 HPV16 HPV E7.

10 Citations

11 1. McLaughlin-Drubin, M.E. and Münger, K., 2009. The human papillomavirus E7 oncoprotein.
12 *Virology*, 384(2), pp.335-344.

13 2. Yang, H., Lv, X., Li, X., Mao, L., Niu, Z., Wang, T., Zhuang, T. and Huang, Q., 2021. ZNF213
14 facilitates ER alpha signaling in breast Cancer cells. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 11, p.638751.

15 3. Liu, Y., Su, P., Zhao, W., Li, X., Yang, X., Fan, J., Yang, H., Yan, C., Mao, L., Ding, Y. and Zhu, J.,
16 2021. ZNF213 negatively controls triple negative breast cancer progression via Hippo/YAP signaling.
17 *Cancer science*, 112(7), pp.2714-2727.

18 GSE240750
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28